

Thiazolidones. Part VII. Synthesis of 5-Alkyl/aryl-2-aryl/benzyl-imino-4-thiazolidones

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Various aryl- and benzyl-thioureas have been condensed with α -bromo-acids to yield 5-alkyl/aryl-2-aryl/benzylimino-4-thiazolidones.

In continuation of our previous works¹, aryl- and benzyl-thioureas have been condensed with α -bromovaleric², α -bromocaproic², α -bromo-*p*-chlorophenyl-, α -*p*-dibromophenyl-, and α -bromo-2, 4-dichlorophenyl-acetic acids to furnish the corresponding 5-alkyl/aryl-2-aryl/benzylimino-4-thiazolidones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Arylthioureas were prepared from the corresponding amines. Benzylthioureas were prepared as described previously¹. α -Bromo-fatty acids were prepared by bromination of the corresponding fatty acids³. α -Bromo-arylacetic acids were prepared as described by Raval and Trivedi¹.

α -Bromo-acids were condensed with aryl- and benzyl-thioureas as described by Raval and Trivedi¹.

Thiazolidones (yield about 60%) were crystallised from ethanol. The compounds are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

5-Alkyl/aryl-2-aryl-imino-4-thiazolidones.

No.	R.	X.	M.P	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Reqd..
1.	Propyl ⁿ	H	138°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	13.5	13.7
2.	"	<i>o</i> -Cl	125°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON ₂ ClS	11.7	11.9
3.	"	<i>o</i> -OMe	175°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	11.9	12.1
4.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	215°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ON ₂ ClS	10.5	10.6
5.	"	<i>o</i> -Cl	294°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	9.6	9.5
6.	"	<i>m</i> -Cl	206°	"	9.2	"
7.	"	<i>o</i> -Me	294°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ ClS	9.9	10.1
8.	"	<i>m</i> -Me	162°	"	10.2	"
9.	"	<i>p</i> -Br	160°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ON ₂ ClBrS	8.1	8.4
10.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	H	224°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ON ₂ BrS	9.4	9.2
11.	"	<i>m</i> -Cl	112°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ON ₂ ClBrS	8.2	8.4
12.	"	<i>p</i> -Br	116°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Br ₂ S	7.4	7.5
13.	"	<i>p</i> -Me	280°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ BrS	9.0	8.9
14.	"	2,4-DiCl	296°	C ₁₅ H ₉ ON ₂ Cl ₂ BrS	7.9	7.7
15.	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	H	210°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	9.3	9.5

1. This Journal, 1959, 36, 733; 1960, 37, 353, 435.

2. *Ibid.*, 1956, 33, 473; 1958, 35, 657.

3. Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 1951, p. 121.

TABLE II

5-Alkyl/aryl-2-benzylimino-4-thiazolidones.

No.	R.	X.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1.	Propyl ⁿ	H	139°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S	12.0	12.9
2.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	150°	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ ON ₂ ClS	11.5	11.3
3.	"	3,4-DiMe	142°	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ ON ₂ S	11.8	11.8
4.	"	<i>p</i> -Br	140°	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ ON ₂ BrS	9.9	9.8
5.	Butyl ⁿ	<i>o</i> -Br	152°	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ ON ₂ BrS	9.3	9.4
6.	<i>p</i> -ClPh	H	178°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ ClS	10.3	10.1
7.	"	<i>o</i> -Cl	176°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	8.9	9.1
8.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	200°	"	9.2	"
9.	"	<i>m</i> -Me	168°	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ON ₂ ClS	9.9	9.7
10.	"	<i>p</i> -Me	172°	"	9.4	"
11.	"	3,4-DiMe	168°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₂ ClS	9.2	9.3
12.	"	2,5-DiMe	166°	"	9.5	"
13.	"	<i>p</i> -Br	174°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ ClBrS	8.0	8.1
14.	<i>p</i> -BrPh	H	185°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ BrS	9.1	8.9
15.	"	2,5-DiMe	280°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ ON ₂ BrS	8.0	8.2

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